

EMPLOYMENT IN THE PRODUCTION SECTOR IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT AND DIGITALIZATION OF ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The active impact of innovative processes and the digitalization of the economy on the labor market as a whole and the structure of production in particular, entails a change in the structure of employment of the population. The article discusses the structure of employment in the manufacturing sector in the context of innovative development. The tendency of a stable decline in employment in the manufacturing sector is analyzed, with an increase in job creation mainly in the service sector. When developing programs to transfer enterprises to an innovative development model, their social consequences must be taken into account, taking into account the strengthening of the country's economic security.

Key words: employment, production sector, innovation, digitalization, development.

In the industrialized countries of the world, the factors of economic growth have recently changed. The main growth factors are those that ensure the innovative development of a particular country. One of the main factors of innovative development is: compliance of the quality of the labor force with the needs of enterprises. At the present stage in the system of market structures, a significant role is assigned to the labor market, which coordinates the demand and supply of labor force, provides the economy with the necessary labor force, and mediates the process of employment of the population [1]. The labor market as an integral part of the market economy is a system of social relations in agreement interests of employers and hired labor.

The labor market in the conditions of innovative development is being formed under the influence of a number of factors that ensure the unity of both the economy of the country as a whole and its individual subsystems. Special Role here it is given to technical progress, informatization and computerization of production and services [2].

The effective result of the interaction of innovative technologies and employment in practice depends on macroeconomic trends, the ongoing economic policy and sociopolitical factors [3].

Technological innovations and the strengthening of the service nature of the economy are changing the nature of industrial relations in the field of employment. Innovations actively influence the structure of production, and from here - the structure of employment.

Employment in the manufacturing sector of most of the developed and many developing countries, since the mid-1990s, has steadily declined, and new jobs have been created predominantly especially in the service sector. Note that, in turn, for the service sector the instability of jobs is characteristic - here both the creation and fewer jobs than in industry how service businesses are more volatile. However, in general. The service sector creates more jobs than it loses. This influence is especially noticeable in single-industry towns, since the vast majority of their population is employed in one or more two enterprises. Technical modernization of these enterprises, their reprofiling not only changes the structure of production personnel, but also contributes to the growth of structural unemployment.

After all, during the technical renovation of an enterprise or its reprofiling, there arises an objective need to stop for a while. During this period, a small number of highly qualified workers can actually be involved, who are able to set up and adjust new equipment, re-profiling it for the production of new products. Another part of the workers is either in a state of unemployment or is in retraining.

Based on this, when developing a program to transfer an enterprise, and even more so the entire economy of the country, to an innovative development model, it is imperative to take into account its social consequences in order to prevent the mass dismissal of workers and the duration of their stay in a state of forced labor.

The organization and functioning of the labor market, as an important component of a market economy, should focus on solving such important problems as ensuring the effective use of labor potential, it requires taking into account a whole range of factors.

First, the realization of individual ability to work should orientate employers towards obtaining maximum returns from each worker and stimulate payment to the hired employee wages in accordance with his qualifications and completed work.

Secondly, an important role in improving the efficiency of labor activities of an employee belongs to the introduction of preferential taxation and lending for those industries and regions in which it is advisable to increase the number of jobs and the use of direct payments to enterprises for each hired worker.

Thirdly, through the regulated labor market, the economic interests of the subjects of labor relations are coordinated, a competitive environment is provided for each of the parties to market interaction, and a balance is maintained between the demand for labor and its supply. It is indisputable that the low level of innovation activity in industry does not contribute to increasing its competitiveness in the world market, including the European one.

The area of active innovation activity should be covered:

- creation of new energy and resource saving technologies;
- development of information communications and technologies;
- expansion of domestic information and computer networks, digitalization of the economy;
- development of domestic import-substituting technologies with high level of competitiveness;
- the revival of the rocket and space industry, aircraft construction;
- conversion of the military-industrial complex;
- development of social infrastructure, especially in rural terrain.

This problem requires special attention and careful research, especially in the context of the digitalization of the economy. In the process of introducing new technologies, some workers will be forced out of their jobs. are in the most vulnerable position workers performing routine and amenable to "Codification" operations.

Only if existing standards are achieved in all spheres of public life of our state, inherent in economically developed countries, it is possible to reduce economic, in fifty investment, social and other risks of weakening the economic security of the country.

References:

1. Balcerowicz-Shkutnik M., Soyka E. Shkutnik. The impact of innovation processes on changes in the labor market (on the example of the Silesian region of Poland). / Proceedings of the XI International Conference "Russian regions in the focus of change".
2. Jorgenson, D.W.: Information technology and the U.S. economy. Am. Econ. Rev. 91(1), 1-32 (2001)

3. UNCTAD. Digital Economy Report 2019. Value creation: Implications for Developing Countries. United Nations Publications, Sales No. E.19.II.D.17, New York and Geneva
4. Отабек Ганиевич Набижонов, Зоҳиджон Раббимқул Ўғли Хужамқулов, and Ф. Б. Шакирова. "ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР НЕГИЗИДА БАРҚАРОР ИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ" Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research, vol. 2, no. 4, 2022, pp. 326-334.
5. Nabijonov Otabek Ganiyevich, & Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot Qizi. (2021). THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES IN BUILDING A REGIONAL INNOVATION SYSTEM. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(8), 102–106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5709174>
6. Nabijonov Otabek Ganiyevich (2021). IQTISODIYOTDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI. Scientific progress, 1 (3), 136-139.
7. Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna, & Bakhtiyorov Akhmadbek Feruz-oglu. (2023). OUTCOME OF E-TRADE, CREATING BY ACCELERATING DIGITAL ECONOMY. E Conference Zone, 40–43. Retrieved from <https://econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/1876>
8. Bakhtiyorov, A. (2022). BREAKTHROUGH OF DIGITALIZATION DUE TO THE INNOVATION ECONOMY AND THE EFFECT OF THEIR COLLABORATION FOR ECONOMIC PROSPERITY. BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH-2023, 1(1), 41-49.
9. Bakhtiyorov, A. (2022). Trade And Economic Performance Through Digital Economy. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 24, 720-726.
10. Bakhtiyorov, A. (2023). SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE DIGITIZED GOVERNMENT PRINCIPLE IN PRIVATIZATION. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(7), 55–60. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/18731>

